

APPENDIX A LIST OF QUESTIONS FOR OBTAINING FEEDBACK FROM EXPERTS

Expert Questions	Descriptions
Q1- Do you think the conceptual model is understandable?	Assessing the understandability of a conceptual model in terms of its clarity of representation and relevance to the subject matter without unnecessary complexity.
Q2- Are the key concepts in the conceptual model sufficient?	Determining the sufficiency of critical concepts in a conceptual model and whether they adequately capture the essential elements and relationships of the system.
Q3- Are the connections between modules or concepts correct?	Verifying the correctness of connections between modules or concepts in a conceptual model to ensure that the relationships accurately reflect real-world interactions or dependencies to promote an accurate representation of the system or concept being modelled.
Q4- Is the conceptual model sufficient to understand the use cases of blockchain in managing clinical research?	Assessing the sufficiency of a conceptual model for understanding the use cases of blockchain in managing clinical research and whether it effectively captures the essential elements of blockchain technology and its application to clinical research processes.
Q5- Do you think that the determined concepts are constructed appropriately?	Determining whether the concepts in a conceptual model are constructed appropriately involves assessing whether they accurately represent the components, relationships, and interactions within the system or domain being modeled for ensuring that the concepts are defined clearly, aligned with established principles or theories, and relevant to the context of the model.
Q6- Do you think there are shortcomings or improvement opportunities in the model	It identifies potential shortcomings or improvement opportunities in a conceptual model's effectiveness in representing the target system by considering factors such as the model's clarity, completeness, relevance, and accuracy.